

**LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF NUMERAL COMPONENT OF
PHRASEOLOGY IN ENGLISH AND FRENCH LANGUAGES**

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Abstract: In world linguistics, phraseological units are constantly attracting attention in terms of reflecting the universal and differential state of the features of the national language and speech, representing the history, way of life, customs and traditions of each nation.

In the context of the phraseological landscape of the world, the linguistic features of numerical component phraseologies in the example of the studied languages in a comparative typological aspect, analysis of semantic-correlation aspects, identification of etymological sources and substantiation of the fact that these language units are unique systems play an important role in strengthening linguocultural relations. In world linguistics, there is a need to study phraseological units in modern areas such as anthropocentric, semantic-pragmatic, linguocultural-cognitive, linguopsychological, cognitive-semantic and linguoculturological, identification of differential cases, differentiation of semantic structural aspects, ethno-linguistics analysis of features, scientific study of the etymology of international and universal numerical component phraseologies formed as a result of cultural interactions of peoples is one of the important issues of linguistics.

Without the description of the quantitative definiteness of the reality, neither knowledge, nor human practice, nor communication is possible. In English, the means of expressing ideas of quantity penetrate all the levels of language structure, phraseology as well. The purpose of the article is to investigate phraseological units with numeral components of phraseology in the English and French language. There

is always a special interest in linguistics to numerical phraseological units. Phraseological studies possess great significance as it displays the interrelation between the language and the society. Numerals take active part in the formation of phraseological units thus creating a large phraseological layer. Fixed expressions with numerals are more numerous in number than those with ordinal ones and include expressions with a wide range of numerals such as two, four, five, six, eight, fifty, hundred, thousand. They are commonly used in phraseological units to form a 'human' concept. The results of the investigation showed that the numbers one and two are the most productive numbers in the English phraseological units. The numbers one, three six, nine and ten are used in different senses in these set expressions. The numbers seven and eight are unproductive in the English language. The results of this work can be used for further studying the semantics of numerals in phraseological units and identifying of phraseological units with a numeral component.

Key words: numerals, quantity, phraseological units, ,linguaculture feature, component, semantics-structure, synonymy

Introduction

Everyone wants his/her speech to be rich, emotional and expressive. One of the main ways to achieve this is a reasonable use of different phraseological expressions. Charles Bally, a Swiss linguist and the founder of the theory of phraseology explored the sphere of linguistics and phraseology in the French language, however, his attempt to systematize and classify phraseological units led to the series of other studies in the phraseological sphere in other languages, including English. With the development of civilization and intensive penetration of science into human lives the role of the numerals is constantly increasing, so the research is becoming increasingly relevant

The object of the research is the study of English phraseological combinations with numeral component

This object implies the following tasks of the research:

1. To identify the numeral within phraseological combinations in English and French languages;

2. To contrast the usage of such expressions in sentences.

The theoretical significance of the research is objectified by the recognition of features of numerals in the phraseological expressions, their dominant position in the paradigmatic relations.

The practical significance of the problem is that the study results can be used in the academic process of studying English. The methods of the research are the semantic-structural constative and sampling method, the method of phraseological analysis, the method of phraseological identification, the method of phraseological description.

Results of the research

Numbers are the objective characteristics of the reality. Having created a way of presenting quantity: numbers and figures native speakers gave them a universal form, learned to formalize the results of the knowledge, to formulate the methods of learning. People gave life to the science, without which technological progress is impossible. The quantitative relations are important in the language system as well. The essence of the linguistic phenomenon cannot be revealed if it is not expressed by quantitative relations, objective generalizations can be based only on the quantitative correlations. The semantic modification of English numerals in terms of phraseological combinations is manifested in their ability to change each other, to implement different quantitative filling

(Two heads are better than one; four eyes see more than two), *to be used in the stylistic devices of antithesis, hyperbole* (thousand pardons; one to thousand)

In French language we use the “Deux tête valent mieux qu’une” (“Ikkiti bosh bittasidan yaxshiroq”)

Phraseological units reflect a specific and expressive way in which the people live their lives,

their interests, concerns and customs, their historic and spiritual evolution, their ethic and aesthetic systems of values .

Fixed phrases of English have their own, national, peculiarities. Components of these phraseological units can be characterized as units that have structural and semantic features together with their own unique particularities. The goal of this article is to analyze the function of numeral components in English phraseological units. The equivalents of these set expressions were also determined. Numbers evoke acts, characters, and legendary situations and bear the mark of the authority that the reference to the community's patrimony gives them. Either the phraseme undertakes the symbol in totality, or it retains only its numeral, the number functions as a symbol and carries all memory of an exterior context. When combined with a noun, the numeral forms along with it a syntactic unit, a single part of speech. However, when they are part of a phraseme, numerals look different. Only a limited part of the cardinal and ordinal numerals can establish a phraseological relation, and these are mostly simple numerals. Cardinal and ordinal numerals have the most frequent occurrence, while collective numerals are found less frequent in phrasemes. A feature of the phrasemes is that, not only one or two of its components may interchange, but its entire lexical structure may also vary . The phrasemes with numerals reflect both man's interior and exterior features. The use of the number component in phraseological combinations is approximate and uncertain according to the status of social indicators. In English a wide range of numerals such as two, four, five, six, eight, fifty, hundred, thousand. are commonly used in phraseological units to form a 'human' concept.

For example: Between two stools one goes to the ground; once bitten twice shy; there are two sides to every question ; fool at forty is a fool indeed; horse stumbles that has four legs; keep a thing seven years and you will find a use for it; old men are twice children; rain before seven, fine at eleven; genius is one percent inspiration and ninety-nine percent perspiration; a cat has nine lives; a stitch in time saves nine; two is company, but three is none; four eyes see more than two; first catch your hare. Thereby in the world mind set the numerals have sacred

meaning except cardinal, ordinal and collective ones .

There are expressions about the meaning of which are easy guess without knowing the history of origin. Quite often there are similar phraseological units with numerals. But, the meanings of

some phraseological units are not incomprehensible even native speakers cannot explain, without knowing the background. Expressions with numeral “two” “To have two strikes against one” — to be at a decided disadvantage. He’s got two strikes against him for coming into work late. If he, does it again, the boss said he’d be fired.

“No two minds think alike” — It is better to have the power of two people's minds to solve a problem or come up with an idea than just one person on their own. I want everyone to get into pairs to come up with the solution, because two heads are better than one.

“Not care two straws” = “care a bit two straws” – to not care in the slightest about something or someone; to attach no importance to someone or something; care little or not at all. I do not care two straws about making money, I just want to make life better for others.

“(As) cross as two sticks” — angry, irritated, in a bad mood, peeved, vexed, upset, irked, piqued, out of humor, put out, displeased, galled, resentful. This expression is a play on the two senses of cross, firstly ‘bad-tempered’ and secondly intersecting. I was in a good mood when I woke up this morning, but now I feel cross as two sticks after getting stuck in traffic.

“Between two fires” = “Fall between two stools” — between two sources of conflict, being attacked from two sources or sides simultaneously. In French language “Entre deux feux”.(Ikki o’t orasiga kirmoq).Ex :Une jeune femme enciente prise entre deux feux. In Uzbek language we use the phrase “Ikki o’t orasida qolmoq”. This phraseology with numerals indicates the hopeless situation in which the person turns out to be. When my dad joined my mom in criticizing me, I felt like I was caught between two fires.

“A game that two can play” — something that both parties involved in a situation

could do.

The phrase typically prefaces an act of retaliation. He has been getting here early to impress the boss, so here I am, too — that’s a game that two can play!

“In two shakes (of a lamb’s tail)” — very quickly, in a very short time. If you say that you will do something in two shakes of a lamb’s tail, you mean that you will do it very quickly. I shall be with you in two shakes. Do not worry, I will pick me up in two shakes of a lamb’s tail! In French “En deux coups de queue d’agneau”. (qo’zichoq dumining ikki zarbasida).

“Take somebody down a peg or two” — to reduce or damage one’s ego or pride; to humble or humiliate one; to show someone that they are not as important as they thought. Tom was so rude that the teacher was bound to knock him down a peg or two.

“(As) thick as two short planks” — remarkably stupid, dim-witted, or obtuse. He’s a very skilled football player but he’s as thick as two short planks.

“Fall between two stools” — to be caught between two things and thus unable to adequately do or accommodate both. If something falls between two stools, it fails to achieve either of two aims. This phrase comes from the proverb *between two stools one falls to the ground*, first referred to in English by the medieval writer John Gower in *Confessio Amantis*. The grammar guide falls between two stools — it’s too difficult for a beginner but not detailed enough for an advanced student. In French we use the this expression “Etre assis entre deux chaises” (Ikkita stul orasida o’tirmoq). You can’t sit in two chairs with one butt. You cannot do or accomplish two things simultaneously, so you must be decisive in choosing or pursuing one. You can’t sit in two chairs at the same time. In Uzbek language has a equivalent “Ikki kemaning boshini tutgan g’arq bo’ladi”.

“Have (got) two left feet” — to be unable to dance gracefully; to have awkward or clumsy footwork while dancing. I’m sorry, I can’t dance better. I have two left feet. In French language has a equivalent “Avoir deux pieds gauches=avoir deux left hands” (ikkita chap oyoqlari bor=ikkita chap qo’llari bor) means is to be very clumsy, c’est être très maladroit (qo’pol, no’noq). Have two left feet= not

graceful when moving or playing sport, used to describe a person who dances badly
“(As) like as two peas (in a pod)” — very similar, especially in appearance. The
twins are like two peas in a pod. in French “Se ressembler comme deux gouttes
d’eau=c’est se ressembler trait (Huddi ikki tomchi suvdek o’xshash). This
expression also means very similar.

“Tell somebody a thing or two” — to correct or confront someone about his, her or
their mistaken belief or incorrect point of view. That jerk has been making snide
remarks about the women in our group all night. I’m going to go over there and tell
him a thing or two!

“Two strings to one’s bow” — two or more ways of achieving success or
accomplish some task or activity. Well, at least you have two strings to your bow
with that degree in accounting if your acting career does not take off. I always try
to plan a project with a backup method, in case my first plan falls apart. It is
always good to keep two strings to your bow!

“Put two and two together” — to determine, guess, or infer something from the
available evidence, especially something that is very obvious or easy to guess. I
think he put two together and realized that John had been stealing from him this
whole time.

“There are no two” — no choice, alternative, or other interpretation. It is the same
as “no two ways about it”. No two ways about it. We’re going to have to sell the
farm.

“Kill two birds with one stone” — to succeed in achieving two things in a single
action.

Whenever I’m doing the housework, I like to listen to English language learning
podcasts. That

way, I kill two birds with one stone. in French language also has this idioms “Faire
d’une pierre deux coups” ,(bir tosh bilan ikkita qushni o’ldirmoq), faire deux coupe
double ,in Uzbek “Bir o’q bilan ikki quyonna urmoq” .Measures seven times, cut
once=Look before you leap. In French “Il faut sept fois sa langue dans sa bouche

avant de parler”= réfléchir avant d’agir.(gapirmasdan oldin tilini og’ziga yetti marta olishi kerak)

Conclusion

The studies in the field of phraseological units with numerals are most meaningful in terms of revealing of the cultural and typological features of the concept of number that is reflected in them. The use of the number component in phraseological combinations is approximate and uncertain according to the status of social indicators. The numeral component in phraseology has also linguocultural specificity .Phraseological units with a cardinal numeral component occupy a special place in English The phraseological units with a numeral are characterized by the distinctness and semantic integrity. Despite the sufficient development of modern linguistics, scientists have paid considerable attention to the linguistic and cognitive aspects of numerals in the context of free and phraseological phrases and their differences in comparable languages. Investigated numeral components played the role of intensifier of the conveyed meaning as well.

We analysed sixty-five chosen English phraseological units with cardinal numeral component and determined the semantic meanings of them in the article. As a result of the investigation there were found out such semantics of cardinal numeral components as quantity. The results of the analysis showed that the numbers *one* and *two* are the most productive numbers in the English phraseological units. The use of these numbers is mostly determined by logic and reality. The numbers *three*, *seven and nine* are not very frequently used in the English.

The numbers *two* and *three* bear hyperbolic semantics. The number *seven* is usually associated with something magical and unreal in the English. In the English phraseological combinations, the number *eight* is not productive. Number *ten* is not also frequently used in the English phraseological units. All possible points of view are discussed and four types of words in phraseological units are defined: real words, potential words, “former” words, ghost-words. The process of

phraseological units forming is complicated and continuous theoretically and practically that is connected with the development of civilization and teaching phraseology should consider both linguistic and extra linguistic aspects.

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